

Impact Assessment of Stubble Burning on Human Health and Environment in District Ferozepur (Punjab) -A Functional Analysis

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Abstract

Despite legal obligations, the problems of stubble burning have been rising in the state. The stubble burning has been releasing many harmful gases which are the hazards to human and animal health and also disturb the ecological balance of environment. This issue has become the serious concern of state and central government and draw attention of researchers, scientists, and policy makers etc. to manage the rising problem of stubble burning across the various parts of the country particularly in Punjab state. Keeping in view the present scenario of stubble burning, the present study was designed to know the Impact Assessment of Stubble Burning on Human Health and Environment in Punjab.

Key words: Stubble Burning, Impact, Assessment, Concern, Environment, Ecological balance, Hazards.

Introduction

The Indian agricultural scenario has undoubtedly seen numerous significant changes and achievements. India has gone from a food shortage to a food surplus market because of the green revolution (Kaur and Grover, 2015). The major research and development efforts in India during the green revolution era resulted in varietal breakthroughs in crops, particularly rice and wheat, which offered opportunities to increase crop productivity and cropping intensity at the farm level and also to ensure national food security. In recent years, the Indo-Gangetic Plains of India, the heartland of green revolution technologies, has seen serious consequences of these practices in the form of overexploitation of groundwater resources, causing faster depletion of the ground water table (Rattan et al., 2021), degradation of Punjab soils due to mining of macro and micro nutrients (Benbi, 2018), high levels of pesticides used, posing a major health hazard, and increased emissions (GHGs), followed by static or declining grain yields, rising production costs, shrinking business margins, and environmental deterioration (Forget, 1993; Igbedioh, 1991). The researchers, scientist and various government institutes are much more dedicatedly looking for means to achieve the goal of sustainable agriculture and the Punjab state is known as India's main granary contributing state, contributing almost a quarter of rice and more than a third of wheat to the central region (Gop, 2019). Punjab's contribution of wheat and rice to the central region over the past three decades is almost half during the last three decades. The production of food grains commendably increased from 723 lakh tonnes in 1960-1961 to 2967 lakh tonnes in 2019-20.

Apart from this, productivity of Crop per hectare grown in Punjab is much higher than the average productivity of crops per hectare in India. In 2019-20 per hectare productivity of rice and wheat in Punjab was 4034 kgs. and 5004 kgs. This is because; Punjab has been making use of modern agricultural machines and implements on a large scale. In Punjab, rice is normally grown in May-August and harvested in the months of September-November and Wheat is grown in October-November and harvested in April-May. But, at the time of harvesting these major crops, a lot of residue is created,

which is called stubble. There is little time from harvest to sowing for wheat and rice, so farmers often choose the easiest way to remove crop residue from their fields through burning. This practice of burning crop residue is called stubble burning.

In the past, when harvesting was done manually, there was less stubble generation and it was more manageable for the farmer. But now, with the advent of machinery for harvesting, the amount of stubble generated is very high, making it difficult for farmers to manage. Punjab and Haryana are generally blamed for deteriorating environment and health (Gadde et.al, 2000). Punjab, Delhi and its nearby areas' experience dense smog, fog and haze every year during the crop residue burning season which runs from mid-October to mid-November, along with a deterioration in water and air quality (India.com, 2018). Currently, the burning of crop residues is a prominent problem in the northern states of India, which causes air pollution. The air pollution increasing to a great extent in the month of October in Punjab and Haryana, where lot of fire activities are experienced in the farms as straw left after harvesting. It pollutes the air which leads to many respiratory problems (Prمود and Surrener, 2013). Thus, it is the prominent cause which prompts farmers to use this method to clear their fields, but it causes serious health problems also (Wikimedia, 2016).

Though relative outcomes from burning of agriculture residue are not completely understood but exposure to pollution caused from stubble burning is more. Lot of studies in the recent past have tried to find the components of smoke released into the air by stubble burning but very few have tried to find the effect of different particles on lungs (Shi et.al, 2014). Certain researchers have also concluded long-term effect on children's long functioning because of residue burning. Presently, no particular law restricts the farmers from stubble burning. Thus, keeping in view of taking importance of this current issue for research, this paper will analysis an "Impact Assessment of Stubble Burning on Human Health and Environment in District Ferozepur (Punjab) -A Functional Analysis.

• **Material and Methods**

It has been observed that the problem of stubble burning are mostly prevailing in the areas where the rice-wheat rotation are dominant than other crops. Since the burning of crop residues is major cause of air pollution and generated many health problems, this issue has become the serious concern of state as well as central government. Therefore, the present study has designed to highlight the various reasons of stubble burning in the Punjab state. This research paper described the detail procedure of sampling design, the methods and the statistical tools used for analyzing the sampled data are discussed as under:

• **Sampling design**

The present study was specifically conducted in the Ferozepur district of the Punjab state in the year 2021-22. The study was based on the primary data and a sample of 300 farmers was taken by random sampling technique. The Cochran's formula was used to finalize the sample size of the study. The formula is given below:

$$\text{Sample (n)} = \frac{Z^2 pq}{e^2}$$

Where Z score is significance level which is taken as 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance 'p' is the proportion of population which is taken as 0.5 'q' is 1-p which is 0.5 and 'e' is the margin of error which is vary between 0.05 to 0.1 per cent depending upon the size of population. The Ferozepur district of the Punjab state has 50282 operational holdings and the error of margin has been taken as 0.057 per cent. By using this formula the calculated minimum sample size was around 300. In order to make the sample more represent able, the sample size was widely spread over large number of villages i.e. about 60 villages were covered by selecting five farmers from each village. The detail of sampling design is given in the table 1:

Table 1: Sampling Design of the Study

S. No	Name of the block	Number of village	Number of farmers
1	Ferozepur	10	50
2	GhallKhurd	10	50

3	Guru harSahai	10	50
4	Makhu	10	50
5	Mamdot	10	50
6	Zira	10	50
Total	6	60	300

• **Data collection**

The study was based on primary data and hence the data from sample farmers were collected through well-structured well prepared, pre-tested questionnaire. All socio-economic aspects such as age, family size, income, type of family etc. has been included in the questionnaire. Since the primary focus of the study was to examine the reasons and problems of stubble burning, therefore the questions related to various issues of stubble burning were included in the final questionnaire. In order to draw some significant implications of the study, many statements with regard to the various aspects of stubble burning has been developed and the perception of the farmers in the respect of these statements were collected on likert scales.

Data analysis

The data were analyzed by using the software named as Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS 21). Simple tools such as frequencies, averages and percentage were used to analyse the data, but some analytical techniques such as one-sample t-test, independent t-test were applied to draw some significant implication of the study.

To understand the issue of stubble burning, a variety of relevant literatures have been reviewed and many such statements were developed and the perception of the farmers with respect to the various issues of stubble was assessed at likert scales. The data were compiled by assigning the following codes.

Strongly disagree	1
Disagree	2
Neutral	3
Agree	4
Strongly agree	5

Hence, the interpretation of the various aspects such as important reasons, problems of stubble burning etc. has been drawn by considering the value of mean score. More is the value of mean score, more important is the reason and vice versa. The perceived reasons of stubble burning are supposed to vary in the sample. It is also assumed that the frequency distributions of the sample respondents with regard to different aspects of stubble burning are differ from each other in the sample. One sample t-test has been applied by considering the following hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis (H₀): The mean score of different aspects of the stubble burning such as reasons, problems, etc. is similar to hypothesized mean value i.e. equal to 3.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): The mean score of different aspects of the stubble burning such as reasons, problems, etc. is differ significantly from the hypothesized mean value i.e. not equal to 3. The form of the model is given below:

$$t - Test = \frac{\bar{X} - \mu}{\sigma \sqrt{n}} \text{ Where;}$$

\bar{X} = Sample mean

μ = Population mean

σ = Standard deviation

n = no of respondents

Cumulative cube-root method- Classification of sample farmers according to impact assessment of stubble burning on human health and environment.

The perception of sample farmers with respect to the impact of stubble burning on different segments of the society such as human health and environment have assessed on liker scales which are discussed in detail. Based on these responses, the impact level of stubble burning was categorized into three levels i.e. low, medium and high by using cube-root method. The formula is given below:

$$\text{Low} = L + \frac{T/3 - c.f}{\sqrt[3]{f}} \times C$$

$$\text{Medium} = L + \frac{2T/3 - c.f}{\sqrt[3]{f}} \times C$$

High = greater than the value of medium level

Where L is the lower limit of class interval

T is the total sum of cumulative frequency

c.f is the cumulative frequency of corresponding class interval

$\sqrt[3]{f}$ is the cube root of the frequency

C is the value of class interval

Functional analysis

It has been noticed that the socio-economic status of the farmer households influenced the impact level of stubble burning on human health and environment. The concern of stubble burning is assumed to be varied with different socio-economic status of the sample farmers. The significant implications of impact assessment of stubble burning on human health, and environment have been drawn on the basis of the relationship of impact level of stubble burning with different socio-economic characteristics of the sample farmers by using t-test. Mathematically it is explained as under:

T-test (Independent samples)

This test was applied to compare the mean difference of impact level of stubble burning according to marital status. The equation is as follows:

$$t\text{-test} = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{S} \times \sqrt{\frac{n_1 n_2}{n_1 + n_2}}$$

\bar{X}_1 = Mean value of various attributes of married respondents

\bar{X}_2 = Mean value of various attributes of un-married respondents

n_1 = number of observations corresponding to married respondents

n_2 = number of observation corresponding to un-married respondents

S = Combined standard deviation

The value of S is calculated as under:

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(X_1 - \bar{X}_1)^2 + \sum(X_2 - \bar{X}_2)^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}}$$

Degree of freedom = $n_1 + n_2 - 2$

• Result, Findings and Discussions

Impact of stubble burning on Human Health -Stubble burning are releasing very harmful gases which adversely affects the human health particularly the weak immunity human beings. The impact of stubble burning on human health have been assessed on likert scales. The frequency of sample farmers

with respect to different diseases and the problems that are emerged during the time of stubble burning is presented in the Table 2.

Table 2: Impact of stubble burning on Health

Sl.	Problems	SD	D	N	A	SA	Mean score	t-stat	p-value
1.	Bronchial problems (inflammation of lungs due to infection or other causes)	38	9	29	101	123	3.87	11.41*	<0.001
2.	Irritation in eyes (eyes feel as being burnt)	17	6	41	67	169	4.22	18.87*	<0.001
3.	Coughing (congestion in the chest)	18	17	53	93	119	3.93	13.87*	<0.001
4	Experience nose irritation due to smoke	18	10	21	153	98	4.01	16.88*	<0.001
5	Experience throat irritation due to smoke	17	8	48	124	103	3.96	15.70*	<0.001
6	Asthma (shortness of breath, congestion in the chest)	20	32	45	118	85	3.72	10.59*	<0.001
7	Emphysema (lung disease due to exposure to smoke, toxic chemicals etc.)	23	30	58	127	62	3.58	8.79*	<0.001
8	Respiratory allergies (hay fever caused due to over reaction of the immune system to a stimulus like dust, smoke, air pollutants etc.)	35	15	53	82	115	3.76	9.89*	<0.001
9	Other lung and heart disease	21	20	62	108	89	3.75	11.17*	<0.001
10	Health problem gets aggravated during stubble burning	23	23	60	90	104	3.76	10.82*	<0.001
11	Severe neurological and cardiovascular diseases	18	56	79	85	62	3.39	5.73*	<0.001
12	Any other problem	240	3	14	17	26	1.62	18.25*	<0.001

SA= strongly agree, A= agree, N= neutral, DA= disagree, SD = strongly disagree Test score=3.00

*significant at one per cent level of probability

The impact of stubble burning on human health has been explained on the basis of mean score which has been worked out by considering the likert scales as the responses of the farmers with respect to various problems. The more is the mean score, higher is the impact and vice versa. The irritation in eyes and nose due to smoke were emerged as the most important problems as the value of mean score was more than 4.0 in favour of these two problems. The mean score with respect to the problems such as coughing (congestion in the chest), bronchial problems (inflammation of lungs due to infection or other causes), respiratory allergies (hay fever caused due to over reaction of the immune system to a stimulus like dust, smoke, air pollutants etc.), Health problem gets aggravated during stubble burning, other lung and heart disease, asthma (shortness of breath, congestion in the chest), emphysema (lung disease due to exposure to smoke, toxic chemicals etc.) and severe neurological and cardiovascular diseases were ranged between 3 to 4. This indicates that most of the farmers were likely to 'agree' and 'strongly agree' with respect to various problems that are most likely to happen during the period of stubble burning.

The perception of sample respondents with respect to the impact of stubble burning on human health are supposed to differ from each other. The test score or hypothesized mean was fixed at '3' which is the median of 1 to 5 scales. One sample t-test has been applied by considering the following null and alternative hypotheses:

Null Hypothesis (H₀): The mean score of different problems of stubble burning is similar to hypothesized mean value i.e. equal to 3.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): The mean score of different problems of stubble burning is differ significantly from the hypothesized mean value i.e. not equal to 3.

One sample t-test revealed that the calculated p-value turned out to be less than 0.01 and hence, the null hypothesis stand rejected. This shows that the perception of sample farmers with respect to various health problems that are emerged during the time of stubble burning differ significantly in the sample.

Impact of stubble burning on environment

The emission of harmful gases during the stubble burning disturbs the eco-system and thus becomes the primary cause environmental degradation. The Likert scales were used to assess the impact of stubble burning on environment. The frequency distribution of sample farmers with respect to different environmental problems that are emerged during the time of stubble burning is presented in the Table 3. The impact of stubble burning on environment has been interpret on the basis of mean score which has been worked out by considering the likert scales as the responses of the farmers with respect to various environmental problems. The more is the mean score, higher is the impact and vice versa. The problem namely 'Reduces visibility due to smog' was emerged as the most important problems as the value of mean score was the highest (4.01) in favour of this problem. The mean score with respect to the environmental problems such as contributor to air pollution, decreases the oxygen supply, produces black carbon (which strongly absorb solar radiation), sources of gaseous pollutant, low wind speed and drop in ambient temperature, contributor to soil pollution, responsible for haze, produces brown carbon (which scatters solar radiation) and responsible for melting of Himalayan glaciers were ranged between 3 to 4. This indicates that most of the farmers were likely to 'agree' and 'strongly agree' with respect to these environmental problems that are most likely to happen during the period of stubble burning.

Table 3: Impact of stubble burning on environment

Sl.	Problems	SD	D	N	A	SA	Mean score	t-stat	p-value
1.	Contributor to air pollution	27	21	26	108	118	3.90	12.42*	<0.001
2.	Sources of gaseous pollutant	21	30	59	91	99	3.72	10.28*	<0.001
3.	Decreases the oxygen supply	21	38	48	66	127	3.80	10.67*	<0.001
4.	Produces black carbon (which strongly absorb solar radiation)	24	35	23	128	90	3.75	10.59*	<0.001
5.	Produces brown Carbon (which scatters solar radiation)	27	44	59	111	59	3.44	6.22*	<0.001
6.	Reduces visibility due to smog	33	3	41	73	150	4.01	13.57*	<0.001
7.	Low wind speed and drop in ambient temperature.	24	26	65	92	93	3.68	9.63*	<0.001
8.	Contributor to soil pollution	21	38	59	80	102	3.68	9.38*	<0.001
9.	Responsible for Haze	42	20	51	99	88	3.57	7.34*	<0.001
10.	Responsible for melting of Himalayan glaciers	48	38	72	57	85	3.31	3.80*	<0.001
11.	Any other	241	3	8	25	23	1.62	18.25*	<0.001

SA= strongly agree, A= agree, N= neutral, DA= disagree, SD = strongly disagree

Test score=3.00

*significant at one per cent level of probability

The perception of sample respondents with respect to the impact of stubble burning on environment is observed to vary in the sample. One sample t-test has been applied by considering the following null and alternative hypotheses:

Null Hypothesis (H₀): The mean score of different environmental problems is similar to hypothesized mean value i.e. equal to 3.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): The mean score of different environmental problems is differ significantly from the hypothesized mean value i.e. not equal to 3.

One sample t-test revealed that the calculated p-value turned out to be less than 0.01 and hence, the null hypothesis stand rejected. This shows that the perception of sample farmers with respect to various environmental problems that are emerged during the time of stubble burning differ significantly in the sample.

- **Impact assessment of stubble burning on human health and environment**

The perception of sample farmers with respect to the impact of stubble burning on different segments of the society such as human health and environment have assessed on liker scales which are discussed in the above section in detail. Based on these responses, the impact level of stubble burning was categorized into three levels i.e. low, medium and high by using cube-root method.

The classification of sample farmers according the impact level of stubble burning on human health and environment is given in Table 4. Based on the aggregate sum of score, the respondents having score between 15-41 was classified as low level, the respondents having score between 42-51 termed as medium level and the respondents having score more than 51 may be regarded as high impact of stubble on human health. Out of total sample, the proportion of farmers indicating low, medium and high impact of stubble burning on human health estimated to the tune of 36.33, 39.00 and 24.67 per cent, respectively.

Impact of stubble burning on environment indicated that the respondents having score between 14-36, 37-45 and more than 45 may be regarded as low, medium and high impact of stubble burning. Out of total sample, the proportion of farmers indicating low, medium and high impact of stubble burning on environment worked out to be 37.67, 32.33 and 30.00 per cent, respectively.

It is evident from the analysis that all sample farmers conceived certain levels of implications of stubble burning on both human health and environment. As such, the percent share of the farmers representing 'high' impact of stubble burning turned out to be the highest i.e. 30 per cent in case of environment, while the respective figures were 24.67 per cent in case of human health. Therefore, among the different implications of stubble burning, the impact on environment may be considered as the most severe impact as reported by sample farmers.

Table 4: Distribution of sample farmers according to impact level of stubble burning on human health and environment

Impact level	Score	Number	Percent
Human Health			
Low	15 - 41	109	36.33
Medium	42 - 51	117	39.00
High	52 - 60	74	24.67
Environment			
Low	14 - 36	113	37.67
Medium	37 - 45	97	32.33
High	46 - 55	90	30.00

- **Summary**

Stubble burning is reckoned among the major contributors of air pollution causing serious damage to human health and the environment. Stubble burning is releasing very harmful gases which adversely affects the human health particularly the weak immunity human beings. The irritation in eyes and nose due to smoke were emerged as the most important problems. Apart from this, problems such as coughing (congestion in the chest), bronchial problems (inflammation of lungs due to infection or other causes), respiratory allergies (hay fever caused due to over reaction of the immune system to a stimulus like dust, smoke, air pollutants etc.), Health problem gets aggravated during stubble burning, other lung and heart disease, asthma (shortness of breath, congestion in the chest), emphysema (lung disease due to exposure to smoke, toxic chemicals etc.) and severe

neurological and cardiovascular diseases are big concern. The emission of harmful gases during the stubble burning also disturbs the eco-system and thus becomes the primary cause environmental degradation such as contributor to air pollution, decreases the oxygen supply, produces black carbon (which strongly absorb solar radiation), sources of gaseous pollutant, low wind speed and drop in ambient temperature, contributor to soil pollution, responsible for haze, produces brown carbon (which scatters solar radiation) and responsible for melting of Himalayan glaciers.

• Suggestions

Based on the outcome of the present study, following suggestive measures are to be advised for controlling stubble burning in the state:

- Human health is the most important concern during stubble burning period. An advisory of prevention measures should be initiated to the common people during the peak burning season. Some preventive measures such as mask, goggles etc needs to be adopted by the general public during peak season.
- The problem namely 'Reduces visibility due to smog' emerged as the most important effect of stubble burning on environment. Owing to the low visibility due to smog, the incidence of accidents increases to a large extent during the period of stubble burning which needs to be addressed by Government and the major cause of this increased rate of accidents due to smog is stubble burning which needs a permanent solution.
- Good human health, fertile soil, agriculture industry, tourism are the important factors for development of any economy and all these sectors are reported to be severely affected by the smog. It is evident that the stubble burning adversely effects air quality, posed risks to neighboring fields, commuters, communities, building etc. and hence disturbs the movement of the people which adversely affects the economic activities. Taking into account the economic loss and increase expenditure on social cost, some sincere efforts need to be undertaken to control the stubble burning.
- It is evident that the intensity of delivering seminars and camps regarding the awareness of adverse and harmful effects of stubble burning was very low in the premises of stubble burning areas which need to be increased. The monitoring of pollution control bodies was observed to effective only at the time of stubble burning, while it remains ineffective during rest of the period. Hence, all the pollution control agencies are advised to have regular visit in the premises of stubble burning areas in prior to stubble burning season.
- The concern of stubble burning is assumed to be varied with different socio-economic status of the sample farmers. A sensitivity analysis has been carried out to examine the concern of farm households with respect to the impact of stubble burning on human health and environment. Therefore, the model advised to educate the younger cultivators to increase the concern of stopping stubble burning in case of environment so far the society and the overall economy is concerned.

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